

EFFICACY OF ALEDRA PARASITICA A. RICH IN LEPROSY

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INTRODUCTION

Leprosy is one of the common problem. According to ancient literature Leprosy is found since i. e. from Vedas to Samhitas and in puranas, this is a karmaj and papaj vyadhi, so that the kushthi is always hated by the society from the ancient times till today. Keeping in view of treatment, essential nursing and treatment to kushthi and to help in the eradication programme of leprosy.

There are some important plants described in Samhitas & Nighantus, which are used in kushtaroga since long such as

1. Khadirsar (Acacia catechu)
2. Tuvrak tail (Hydnocarpus wightiana)
3. Brahmi. (Bacopa monniert)
4. Til tail.
5. Bhallatak (Semecarpus anacardium)
6. Bakuchi (Psoralea corylifolia)
7. Amaltas (Are fistula).

In this study, the role of other important plant kushthi with its traditional uses and effects of a single drug treatment on kushtha.

The traditional herbs of this area are such as Vriddhadarak Chaudhara (*Ipomea petaloidea*), Rama Narayan Booti (*Alectra parasitica*) & Kewati (*costus speciosus*) etc. Out of three above plants, one plant Ram Narayani Booti the root of vitex negundo ‘‘*Alectra parasitica*’ is very much useful in leprosy and collected from forest range with its traditional uses.

1. A Short Botanical Description is as Under

S. N. Kushthari.

H. & T. N. Nirgundi mool kund.

L. N. *Alectra pasesitica* A. Rich.

Ver Chitrakutansis M. A. Rau. Family-scrophulariaceae.

Description

Annual parasitic plant specially growing On the roots of vitex negundo and belonging to scrophulariaceae family.

Stem :- Erect 10 to 15 c. m. high delicate Rhizome.

Root :— Nodular, internally yellow and outer surface is red in fresh condition and after drying the roots are changed to black colour, size 3 to 50 c. m. long and bitter in taste.

Flower :- Flower in spike, small, yellow Orange colour.

Fl. time :- April and May.

Part used :- Rhizome and whole plants.

Distribution :- Specially growing on the roots of vitex negundo in Chitrakoot forest area in Banda district.

Chemicals contains :— Rhizome contains saxafrin and flowering stem contain manitol, Alkali, sterol and Tannin.

Local uses :- The local saharias and Sadhus use it in galit kushtha and Rheumatism, since long.

Mode of uses

The single plant of kushthari is used in powder form 2 to 3 gms B. D. with cow’s urine for 2 to 4 months regularly. They also used it in other skin diseases.

3. According to pharmacological study reports it is also a useful drug for Leprosy and the report is as under

Anti leprotic indicated in lepromatous and tuberculoid type of leprosy, Scientific Clinical trials concluded that tuberculoid type of leprosy patients were relieved of tingling in 6 months.

This accompanied with diminution of the area of anaesthetic patch. The tuberculoid cases were bacilli free from the very beginning.

In lepromatous cases the raised erythematous patches become flattened and lose their erythema and are changed to dark hue in two months times. The lesions to respond first were on the extremities, than those on trunks and last of all the facial responded. After 6 months the number of acid fast bacilli decreases to an enormous extent. The nasal smear become negative after 6 months of therapy.

Dose : 2 to 3 gram BD

CONCLUSION

As per getting the information regarding folklore and trials as well as its characters of above mentioned plant, it is necessary to assess its efficacy on leprosy. If the folklore other claimed use are confirmed the drug may prove to be cheapest one for the leprosy and helpful in the eradication programme for aforesaid diseases.